

METAL MATRIX COMPOSITES EVOLUTION AND PROSPECTS

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ABSTRACT

The relatively high density of most MMC arises from treating issues such as compatibility, corrosion resistance and adhesion, as well as from reinforcement content. Thus they offer good hot strength and exceptional compressive strength but their specific tensile properties are unexceptional. Metal-organic laminates are better suited to large structures operating below 100°C. Composition and process studies have reduced cost for those engineering components which require special combinations of properties. Certain MMC are also uniquely stable, for electronic platforms and parts. Potential improvements are indicated in the design of reinforcements and in the balance between properties and ease of fabrication.

PERSPECTIVE

"History is a set of lies agreed upon" (N.Bonaparte)

Although we are still too close to tell, it is likely that the fifties will rate as the most important decade for composite science. It was then that it became entirely clear how to prepare strong solids both from brittle and from ductile materials. Towards the end of that decade one knew for sure that fine single crystals of silicon carbide really could be strained elastically by at least 2%, to give tensile strengths around 10GPa or more. But it took another decade to learn how to prepare them in quantity [1], to clean, fractionate and align them and to incorporate them [2] by pressure infiltration, Fig. 1. By this time many of the precursor-based fibres we know today were also becoming available.

The sixties must rate as a decade of great optimism and rapid development of advanced composites technology, principally towards perceived aerospace needs, with strong support from national governments. In a way this was all too late. Certainly in Europe by 1975 Concorde was coming into service built of an aluminium alloy developed in the early 1930s. The Airbus A300 and the Tornado multi-role aircraft were also well advanced and likewise owed little to composites. So too for the 747 and the Apollo moon walk.

Figure 1. Stability of aligned SiC_w cast in aluminium (x350)

Figure 2. CF cast in Mg (1974) crumbles 1995

Metallurgists rightly felt that aluminium was wonderful stuff - which it is - and that composites were something too esoteric to be useful. There was also a general lack of engineers experienced in composites, though they had all heard of the fate of CFRP fan blades in the RB 211 engine (1970). So many preferred to remain inexperienced.

Thus there was some impatience of scientists with engineers and of managers with everyone. The fibres, matrices and composites were there, but serious applications were hard to find. Development was proceeding via "demonstrator" or parallel "ghosting" programmes which avoided dependence on composites. This was the atmosphere of ICCM 1 [3].

PROGRESS

The numerous MMC that have been explored in the intervening twenty years have in common only their theoretical behaviour. The range of metals and reinforcements involved nowadays make up a series of niche markets. The task of reviewing them is of course made easier by elimination, since relatively few reinforcements remain stable in metals during fabrication or service. Full thermodynamic stability is relatively rare. The key factors here are chemical interaction, physical recrystallisation and in the case of electrically conducting fibres, position in the electrochemical series. After twenty years in the benign environment of a laboratory, carbon fibre - magnesium composite which had been pressure-cast has now crumbled away, Fig. 2, whereas reinforced aluminium is at least intact.

Historically an engineer has always been able to get materials which are absolutely stronger, stiffer and more heat-resistant by proceeding up the density scale e.g. from magnesium through aluminium, titanium, steels to the superalloys. Similarly for electronic conduction, from magnesium through aluminium and copper to silver and gold. Other metals such as zinc and the bearing alloys are principally used for their surface properties or for ease of manufacture.

So logically any mechanical reinforcements need to be low density ones, just as the formation of aluminides both in superalloys and in titanium lowers density as well as increasing strength at temperature. The available reinforcing fibres which approach the low density requirement are of course versions of carbon, boron and boron carbide, silicon carbide and alumina, as well as silica and various aluminosilicates. Some of these substances have also been adopted in "particulate" MMC, though particles are easier to prepare than fibres, so other options have emerged here as well.

Most of these refractory fibres exist in a porous form by virtue of their preparation from precursors, but this has proved to make them more vulnerable to attack, unless they are coated either initially, or by precipitation from the matrix. One can only say with any confidence that aluminium does not attack alumina and that dense silicon carbide also appears stable, but that alloying additions of magnesium and particularly of lithium are much more aggressive. Boron, which is readily attacked by

aluminium, is stable in magnesium and so it appears are the denser forms of alumina.

FUNCTIONS OF THE INTERFACE AND INTERLAYER

MECHANICAL

In all fibrous composites, it is established that the toughest materials are obtained when the bond between fibre and matrix is poor enough to fail along the interface, before a fibre can be broken. Sometimes fibres are clustered together to enhance this effect. Now epoxy matrices are not noted for their high shear strength but it is still possible to create such strong adhesion of epoxy to carbon fibres that the composite product is weak and brittle. So too for MMC but the disbonding in this case involves the sacrifice of good transverse properties when the fibres are actually embedded in the metal. Hence the evolution of multilayer hybrid laminates such as ARALL [4], where light organic fibres of aromatic polyamide in epoxy can carry very high tensile stress in one layer. Such materials can adopt improvements in both organic and metallic materials alike. The strong alloy sheets also contribute shear and compressive strength. Compared with wholly organic composites, this can make for cost-effective use of fibres - two orthogonal sets of fibres would otherwise be needed to reproduce metallic levels of shear stiffness.

In contrast, particulate reinforcements must be strongly bonded to be at all effective, unless the objective is purely to improve mechanical damping. Dedicated fibrous MMC prove an order greater in fracture toughness [5] than particulate ones for this reason.

CHEMICAL

Many coatings and treatments were perhaps ill-advisedly used on fibres to promote "wetting". Developments in fabrication technology have since rendered these unnecessary, except where they increase the bonding of particles.

The prime purpose of contemporary coatings appears to be to block chemical interaction with the matrix and to be poorly adhering, ideally forming a so-called core/sheath structure in which the coating can also carry transverse stress around the fibre, rather than through it.

EXAMPLES

* Even though stable phases of TiC and TiN exist in some gas-turbine superalloys, the pursuit of a separate reinforcement for this purpose seems to have been abandoned in favour of "single crystal" blades.

* Silicon carbide is not stable in titanium but by coating the monofilament with TiB₂ and with graphite [6], tough materials with excellent long-term properties have been obtained of value for engines and airframes alike. Yttria is also a popular barrier material [7].

* Many authors report reduced interaction between aluminium and the more graphitic of carbon fibres, and also the benefit of PG coatings [8] in suppressing attack by light alloys as well as in reducing adhesion. The risk of galvanic corrosion tends to relegate these last materials to space applications where dimensional stability is important i.e. low expansion coefficient and high conductivity. Here the near-theoretical stiffness of graphite fibre prevents expansion in the composite. The stable system of graphite fibre in copper has also been examined for this purpose [9].

* Silicon carbide in its natural state is coated with a very thin oxide layer due to atmospheric exposure and this will be attacked by light alloys. Note that attack of pure aluminium on silica was controlled in the past by small additions of bismuth. Silica fibre has also been coated with graphite lubricant by passing it through a hydrocarbon-rich flame.

* The formation of other barrier phases which develop during infiltration is being studied [10] - a rewarding subject which is full of surprises. Higher melting intermetallic compounds such as Mg_2Si seem effective barriers in light alloy systems, provided that morphology can be controlled.

ADVANCES IN PROCESSES

Since there are few properties which MMC provide which are unique or strategic (though some combinations may be unique) the adoption of them will be much influenced by finished cost, in which process research plays a big part.

Examples are:-

* Titanium alloys of high melting point have been made more user-friendly by developments in diffusion bonding and in superplastic forming, which also enable the effective density of titanium structures to be reduced.

* By rapid solidification of powders or by mechanical alloying the maximum service temperature of light alloys has been increased (as well as improving their ambient properties).

* Hydrostatic consolidation of powders at high pressure is more freely available. Taken together RSR powders and "hipping" also lend themselves to preparing particulate MMC of high quality.

* Pressure casting is overtaking gravity casting as a fast and easily automated way of making net-shape parts [11]. This has already lent itself to mass production of fibre reinforced light alloy pistons for engines, Fig. 3, and has been extended to other larger parts, Fig. 4. The physics of both infiltration and of stirring to incorporate particles now appear to be well understood [12] and the latter has supplanted co-spraying as a favoured technique.

* Particulate MMC lend themselves to secondary fabrication (forging, extrusion, flow-forming etc) but fibrous MMC resist flow in fibre directions and are less amenable unless the fibres are "stringers" from a soft particle phase stretched by co-extrusion (e.g. superconducting oxides).

Figure 3. Cast Al-Si with alumina fibre replaces iron in diesel pistons

Figure 4. Large scale pressure infiltration (A.Clifford, CMT)

ENGINEERING WITH MMC

LARGE STRUCTURES

Large structures which operate in compression tend to be lightly stressed and therefore heavy because bending and buckling collapse inhibits the use of higher stress levels. Conversely where tension can be used predominantly instead, lighter structures can be built e.g. pressurised hulls of aircraft, large rocket motor cases.

The conclusion is therefore that in such structures density reduction techniques are more important than increasing strength, except where specific tensile strength is needed. Apart from the carbon fibre-light alloy systems used in space, MMC in general are not notable for density reduction, compared with other composites or indeed with aluminium-lithium alloys. It is unfortunate that some factions of the airframe industry have resisted the use of ARALL sheet (because of its polyamide-epoxy component) since it is inevitably less dense than metals and MMC, well suited to use at high tensions and tolerant of fastener holes [13]. In a simpler form the same principle is widely used in rocketry, Fig. 5.

Stiffness increases alone are particularly useful if the matrix may be operated at the same strain as before, leading to increased fatigue strength, but this usually implies a need for increased fracture toughness as well.

Increased strength retention at elevated temperatures without increasing density is an attractive option which MMC do provide and in the case of aluminium do so at a low cost, compared with high temperature polymers, which also have more limited performance. Thus a stretched version of Concorde might still adopt MMC. Concorde also has heavy landing gear, comparable in mass with its small payload. Note that in the early proposals for the space plane *Hotol* it was to be trolley-launched, again because of unacceptable mass of undercarriage.

STABLE PLATFORMS

Light, dimensionally stable structures and components are proving an important area for MMC and there are some clear distinctions to be drawn. The generally low or slightly negative expansion coefficient of reinforcements can be used to control the expansion of the matrix, which is usually a light alloy. Note that:

- * It is only the ratio of the elasticities (and the relative volume fractions) which controls net expansion coefficient. Deliberate porosity is allowable. Expansion may be redirected into less critical directions.
- * Good thermal conduction may help to reduce the temperature/dimensional excursions experienced.
- * The expansion movement may be tuned to match existing (e.g. steel) structure. It may also be made reactive or "smart" - as in the bimetallic strip.
- * Additionally, highest directional stiffness and least density may be needed for large structures.

SMALL COMPONENTS

These must usually be mass-produced and may also be space-limited, which drives up working stresses especially for components at the core of engines. Often a combination of properties is sought e.g. good wear resistance, low friction, low inertia and extra temperature performance, typically in high speed machinery of different types. This is the area of hot compressor and stator blades (aligned monofilaments) petrol and diesel pistons (random fibre) and most recently brake housings (particulate) which reduce the unsprung mass of production vehicles. Many other components are being explored via motor sport. The limited output of the human engine can be enhanced via lighter bicycles, better tennis rackets, ski sticks etc. Thus man-portable engines (power tools) are obvious candidates and so are man-portable structures (e.g. extending ladders and scaffolding).

FUTURE TRENDS

Evidently existing MMC have only scratched the surface of applications and they will be more widely used provided they offer combinations of properties either uniquely, or at least cost. They are already linked with buoyant and demanding industries such as aerospace, automobiles and electronics. What then are the implications of materials and process improvements which might occur?

REINFORCEMENTS

Perhaps the most dramatic move would be to treat carbon fibres to disrupt their electrical conductivity and therefore their related corrosion behaviour. This principle has been demonstrated by introducing oxide and halide terminations [14, 15, 16]. In general it is clear that both fibres and particles for MMC should ideally have dense surfaces and virtually hollow cores. This would reduce both matrix attack and density at a stroke. (In the case of particles their reinforcing efficiency would also improve). Reversing the current trend, strong but coarse adhering particles might reduce the constraint on work of fracture in the matrix and certainly would permit blending with finer ones, to increase acceptable volume packing.

Intermediate between equiaxial particles and continuous reinforcements are a range of single crystal platelets, laths and whiskers which ideally need to be aligned for best effect yet cannot very easily be packed to high volume fractions. They can be used to increase hot strength where other fibres might not be affordable. Most notable here are perhaps aluminium borate [17] (comparable in performance with silicon carbide whiskers) and the natural mineral wollastonite [18], a calcium silicate.

The polymeric fibres PBT and PBO possess a straight ladder-like molecular chain which provides more than twice the stiffness of aromatic polyamides and a higher temperature performance as well. In combination with aluminium-lithium alloy they would provide a major advance in hybrid laminates of the ARALL class.

PROCESSES

In the process area one should expect liquid routes to continue to gain ground. At the present time the more elaborate solid-state processes generate higher properties in particulate MMC, but the reasons for this are known and critical differences are likely to diminish.

Pressure infiltration has lately been carried out at reduced melt and preform temperatures [19], by using the exothermic formation of aluminides to avoid premature solidification. Again aluminium infiltration has even been used to form fibre reinforced titanium-aluminide [20]. Thus reactive processing seems destined to become more influential.

A distinction should be drawn between the transient pressure required for infiltration, and the higher and usually more sustained pressure needed to close shrinkage cavities in a solidifying shape. Only a mechanical impulse is needed to cause infiltration - this has been demonstrated over small depths of about a millimetre by use of ultrasonics [21] or by magnetic coupling [12]. Such new techniques are promising for preparing infiltrated tows and other continuous thin sections, at the least.

Figure 5. Kevlar overwound aluminium displaces maraging steel

OPINION

As shown above, there are ample opportunities for improving MMC and hybrid laminates, but there is a need to distinguish theoretical potential from real prospects. The development of better mixtures and processes, particularly liquid routes to near net shape products, seems certain. This area requires careful experimental studies of process physics, the chemistry of interfaces and of metallurgical microstructure. It will attract support because it delivers a component or device, which is what the user wants.

At a time when there has been retrenchment in the fibre industries, the preparation and production of new reinforcements is largely an act of faith. The challenge is to reduce the degree of risk, which might be expressed as follows:- (L-low, M-medium, H-high)

<u>Reinforcement</u>	<u>Benefit</u>	<u>Research risk</u>	<u>Financial Risk</u>
Improved particles and single crystals	L/M	L	M
High modulus polymeric fibres	H	L	M/L
Non-conducting CF (or equivalent)	H	H	L
Dense skin/porous core	M	M	M

Thus an engineer might reasonably expect improved particulate MMC and hybrid laminates to become available - possibly in combination - provided he/she has deep enough pockets. The development of better refractory fibres for MMC is more influential, it provides more opportunity for innovation and will take longer.

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